

Some common predators associated with the brown planthopper in Malaysia

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In mid-1977, the most serious brown planthopper (BPH) outbreak recorded in Malaysia in at least a decade occurred in Tanjung Karang, Selangor. About 1,620 ha were severely affected.

An integrated control approach, adopted to combat the outbreak, included continual surveillance, suitable insecticide application (spraying, mistblowing, fogging, and granular application), light trapping, and cultural methods. Such an approach appeared to be the most appropriate because natural enemies were numerous among the BPH; predators were most active.

The mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, an effective predator of BPH in Southeast Asia, Australia, and the Pacific islands, was important in Malaysia. A light trap in the area of the outbreak monitored the abundance of *C. lividipennis* and BPH. A sharp increase in light-trap catches showed an explosive and sudden outbreak in July, closely associated with a corresponding increase in *C. lividipennis* catches (see figure).

Two other predators — *Casnoidea interstitialis* (Coleoptera: Carabidae) and

Weekly light-trap catches of *Nilaparvata lugens* and its common predators at the Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute Rice Research Station, Tanjong Karang, Malaysia, 1977.

Coccinella arcuata feeding on an adult brown planthopper.

Paederus fuscipes (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae) — were also common in the rice fields. Their sudden increase in the light trap suggests that they may also be active predators of BPH. The coccinellid *Coccinella arcuata*, an active predator of BPH, occurred in large numbers toward the end of the outbreak. Larvae of the predator were observed feeding voraciously on adult BPH (see photo). *C. arcuata* has been reported as

the most common coccinellid predator of BPH in India, Fiji, Australia, and Papua New Guinea.

Serious attempts were made to conserve the major predators during the outbreak. The controlling effects of the predators, together with those of other supplementary measures, helped decrease the BPH population rapidly. The outbreak was suppressed and fully contained by September.

Brown planthopper situation in Bangladesh

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During the 1978 boro, 6 Bangladesh districts — Dacca, Comilla, Tangail, Noakhali, Chittagong, and Chittagong Hill tracts — reported brown planthopper (BPH) outbreaks. Two unconfirmed reports of outbreaks were received from Mymensingh and Dinajpur districts.

The first BPH outbreak was observed during April–May 1976 in the boro crop near Sher-e-Banglanagar, north of Dacca

City. The second was in October 1976 at BRRRI farm in a transplanted aman crop. In 1977, BPH spread to more boro areas. Outbreaks were also reported in the transplanted aman crop from Rajshahi district in northwest Bangladesh.

In Dacca district, BPH outbreaks occurred mainly in the single-rice area in places that remained flooded from June to October. Generally the crop had luxuriant growth, which suggested that the soil was heavily or excessively fertilized. The macroclimate during April–May and October remains almost rain free, sunny, and hot. The microclimate inside rice fields during the

time remains humid. Long-duration or late-planted varieties IR8 and BR3 were mainly affected. Short-duration varieties Chandina and Purbachi were harvested more than a week before the pest population peaked. Hopperburn occurred at flowering to hard dough stage. In hopperburned plots the estimated crop loss was 50–100%.

In several hopperburned fields, the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) population was also high. But the total area with hopperburn caused by WBPH was negligible compared with that with BPH-caused hopperburn. Comilla and Dacca districts also reported hopperburn